

Production and Quality Characterization of Carrageenan Based No-Sugar-Added Mango Spread as an Alternative for Sugar based Mango Jam

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Abstract

Regular jam manufacture is based on the principle of the formation of the pectin- sugar–acid gel that consists of high amount of sugar and calories. Sugar is an essential principle component for the formation of gel in the manufacture of regular jam. The present study investigated alternate procedure to prepare a mango spread similar to the mango jam without adding sugar with the formation of gel by using the hydrocolloid carrageenan. Aspartame (Sugar free gold pallets) was used for sweetening. The hydrocolloid carrageenan was used in the quantity of 2% of the mango pulp for preparation of spread and its physical and sensory properties were studied. Gel strength, rupture force/rupture strength, brittleness/elasticity and adhesiveness values of the product formulation, measured by Texture Analyzer (TA.XT Plus), were found to be 43.50g, 602.40g, 8.90mm and 114.15gs respectively. Gelling/thickening profiles for hydrocolloids were obtained using Rapid Visco Analyser (RVA) with the final viscosity value at 30 °C after a holding period of 10 min as 958cp. Calorific value determined by Bomb Calorimeter was found to be 57.99 Kcal/100g with about 79.65% reduction in calories than that of regular jam. The product showed very similarity in physical as well as sensory properties to the regular mango jam and therefore may be very useful to diabetic patients as well as obese persons.

Introduction

Sweet spreads are available with a wide range of tastes, colors, and textures. They are all made mostly of fruits that have been preserved with sugar, and to some extent they have been thickened or gelled (Basu et al., 2011). These include jams, jellies, marmalades, preserves, and fruit butters. Jam is produced by boiling fruit pulp with enough sugar until it is sufficiently thick and firm to hold the tissues in place and a lot of jam is consumed world-wide (Basu & Shivhare, 2010, Baker et al., 2005, Lal et al., 1998). For every 24.9 kg of sugar, roughly 20.4 kilogram of fruit should be used in the preparation (Siddappaa and Tandon, 1998). Sugar is therefore used to make regular jam, which improves taste, texture, and shelf life. The energy content of one teaspoon (5g) of sugar is about 20 Kcal. In general, sugars are frequently described as having "empty calories." Unfortunately, foods with a lot of added sugar frequently lack important vitamins and minerals. Additionally, because they are enjoyable, it may be simple to overeat. This excess results in the issues of overweight and obesity and may make it difficult to maintain a healthy weight. These issues are linked to a higher risk of developing diabetes, lipid abnormalities, coronary artery disease, high blood pressure, some cancers (including colon and prostate in men and breast, gallbladder, and colon in women), stroke, degenerative arthritis, respiratory issues, sleep disturbances, and gallbladder disease. High sugar intake may also make tooth decay more likely. It is important to reduce the intake of sugars in the diet for these reasons (Edwards et al., 2016, Van Baak & Astrup, 2009, Cannington, 2003). Therefore, to keep our daily sugar and calorie intake to a minimum we may produce spreads/jams using other

sweeteners such as artificial sweeteners, polydextrose, and other sugar substitutes (Sardarodiyani & Hakimzadeh, 2016, Chattopadhyay et al., 2014, Newsome, 1993). For formation of gel we may use hydrocolloids/gelling agents like carrageenan, xanthan gum, locust bean gum etc (Clark, 1991). Many researchers reported and investigated about the gelling properties of different hydrocolloids in food as well as other systems (Saha and Bhattacharya, 2010, Renard et al., 2006, Goncalves et al., 2004, Fu & Rao, 2001, Muñoz et al., 2001, Norziah et al., 2001, Evageliou, 2000, Thakur et al., 1997, Nishinari et al., 1990, Oakenful, 1987, Oakenful 1991, Rees, 1969, Mitchell & Ledward, 1986). This study aimed to find out the possible ways to produce mango spread as close as possible to the regular mango jam using carrageenan as hydrocolloid/gelling agent and aspartame (sugar free gold pellets) as artificial sweetener. This product may prove very helpful to obese and overweight persons who require low calorie foods as well as to diabetic patients who have to control their blood sugar level.

Regular jam production is based on the idea that a pectin-sugar-acid gel forms. When pectin, sugar, and acid are heated in a specific ratio in presence of water, gel is created (Breverman, 1963). In order to create a tangled, interconnected molecular network that is submerged in a liquid media, polymeric molecules must be cross-linked. The water is retained by the polymer network, which stops it from escaping. A combination of weak intermolecular forces, including hydrogen bonds, electrostatic forces, Vanderwaals forces, and hydrophobic interactions, hold the molecules in gels together. The cross-linkages, which typically occur in well-defined structures known as junction zones, contain substantial lengths from two or more polymer molecules rather than being point interactions. These junction zones are essentially created during the gelation process (Hui, 2006). Therefore, sugar is a fundamental ingredient in the formation of jam's gel. Use of hydrocolloids (such as gelatin, xanthan gum, etc.), which can thicken and form gels at very low concentrations, is one potential substitute for forming gel (Williams & Phillips, 2021, Glicksman, 2020, Wüstenberg, 2015, Nishinari & Doi, 2012, Lu et al., 2021). When a hydrocolloid is dissolved in water, the water congregates around the sugar units developing a layer of water with limited mobility. Hydrocolloids have the capacity to organize and regulate water, which is what allows them to gel and thicken. They become hydrophilic substances because of presence of numerous hydroxyl (-OH) groups which significantly improves their affinity for interacting with water molecules. Additionally, they create a dispersion that resembles a colloid and is intermediate between a true solution and a suspension. They are appropriately referred to as "hydrophilic colloids" or "hydrocolloids" in light of these two characteristics (Saha and Bhattacharya, 2010). Jam's rheological behavior has been extensively researched (Basu et al., 2011, Basu and Shivhare, 2010, Basu et al., 2007, Álvarez et al., 2006, Gabriele et al., 2001, Carbonell et al., 1991a, Carbonell et al., 1991b). There has been few comprehensive research on the use of alternative sweeteners in fruit jam preparation (Basu, 2009, Acosta et al., 2008, Houryieh et al., 2005, Bayarri et al., 2004, Gajar and Badrie, 2001, Abdullah and Cheng, 2001, Hyvönen & Törmä, 1983).

Materials and Methods

Ripe Mangoes: Ripe mangoes of Totapuri variety were procured from the local market Nawabganj, Kanpur.

Carrageenan: The hydrocolloid Carrageenan, procured from Himedia (Mumbai, India) was used in the study.

Sweetener: Sugar Free Gold pellets (Zydu Wellness, Sikkim, India) made from aspartame were used as sweetener. Each pellet of 100 mg contains 18 mg of aspartame. Other ingredients include lactose, croscarmellose sodium, colloidal silicon dioxide, magnesium stearate i.p., and polyvinyl pyrrolidone. As it contains aspartame, it is not recommended for children.

Food Colour: For colouring Lemon Yellow Extra (blend of tartrazine and NaCl, Dadajee Dhackjee Ltd., Bhavnagar) was used in the preparations.

Food Flavour:The flavour used was Mango Flavor Ripe (S.1854) purchased from Bush Boake Allen (Chennai, India).

Sugar: Food grade sucrose, of brand name Mawana sugars in 1.0 kg packing was procured from the local market Nawabganj, Kanpur.

Water: drinking water supplied by H. B. T. U., East campus was used in the preparation wherever needed.

Other Chemicals:Sodium benzoate (preservative) and citric acid were purchased from Thomas Baker (Mumbai, India).

Apparatus: Analytical weighing balance (least count 0.1 mg, HR-200, Make A & D Company Ltd., Japan), pH meter (Make Hanna Instruments, Italy), Hand refractometer (Make Erma, Tokyo, Japan), Texture Analyzer, TA.XT Plus (Make Stable Microsystems, UK), Rapid Visco Analyser (Make Newport Scientific, Australia), Bomb Calorimeter (Make Toshniwal Brothers Delhi, India), Mixer grinder (Make Polar) were used in the study.

Preparation of the Products

Two samples were prepared for analyzing quality and similarity: Sample-1, the proposed spread using the hydrocolloid carrageenan and, sample-2, the regular mango jam sample as the control sample.

Preparation of spread (Sample-1) using carrageenan as hydrocolloid

Mango pulp was produced using mango of Totapuri variety. The pH of the pulp and TSS was 4.9 and 14 °Brix, respectively. The spread was prepared similar to the process of regular jam manufacturing except the sugar was replaced by aspartame pellets, carrageenan was added 2% of the pulp for gel formation and sodium benzoate was added as preservative. The recipe of the spread is shown in Table 1. The pH of the pulp was adjusted to 3.1 by addition of 10% (w/v) citric acid solution and measured using a pH meter. Desired amount of hydrocolloid (on pulp basis) is dissolved completely in water with continuous stirring with gentle heating. Fruit pulp and sweetener were added to this. The mix was heated in an open stainless steel pan on an electric coil heater at low temperature and TSS was monitored during boiling. Colour, flavour and preservative were added at the end of boiling. Color solution was prepared by dissolving 15 g colour in 500 ml of water. 25 ml of this solution is used for each sample. Pulp–hydrocolloid–sweetener mix was stirred continuously with a glass-rod during boiling. Heating was stopped when TSS reached 10–11° Brix and the mixture was poured into glass jars and cooled under ambient condition for 24 h for proper setting of the spread. The flow chart for the preparation of spread using hydrocolloids is shown in fig. 1.

Table 1: Recipe used for preparation of mango spread with 2% carrageenan(Basis = 500 g mango pulp).

S. No.	Ingredients	Quantity
1	Carrageenan	10 g
2	Pulp	500 g
3	Water	250 ml
4	Sweetener	10 g
5	Color	25 ml from preparation
6	Mango essence	0.5 ml
7	Preservative	0.7 g

Fig. 1: Flow chart for the manufacture of spread using the hydrocolloid carrageenan

Preparation of Regular Mango Jam (Sample-2)

Regular jam was prepared by ordinary method(Siddappaa and Tandon, 1998). The recipe for the preparation of regular jam is shown in table 2. Flow chart for the manufactureof regular jam is shown in the fig. 2. Mango pulp was weighed and the pH of the pulp was adjusted to 3.1 by addition of 10% (w/v) citric acid solution and measured using a pH meter. Desired amount of sugar and water was added to the pulp and mixture was transferred in an open stainless steel pan. The mix was heated an electric coil heater at low temperature and TSS was monitored during boiling. Colour, flavour and preservative were added at the end of boiling. Color solution was prepared by dissolving 15 g colour in 500 ml of water. 40 ml of this solution is used for the sample. Pulp–pectin–sugar–acid mix was stirred continuously with a glass-rod during boiling. Heating was stopped when TSS reached 68-70° Brix and the mixture was poured into glass jars and cooled under ambient condition for 24 h for proper setting of jam (End point was judged by 68° Brix TSS).

Table 2 Recipe for preparation of Regular jam (Siddappaa and Tandon, 1998)

S. No.	Ingredients	Quantity
1	Mango Pulp	500 g
2	Sugar	500 g
3	Pectin 150 grade	6.25g
4	Citric Acid	5.00g
5	Mango essence	0.9ml
6	Colour	40 ml from the preparation
7	Water	Q.S.

Fig 2Flow chart for the manufacture of regular jam

Analysis of the Products

The prepared samples were subjected to (A) instrumental analysis and (B) sensory analysis. The instrumental analysis included measurement of texture, study of the gelling profile and determination of calorific value. Sensory analysis included scoring test and flavour profile.

A. Instrumental Analysis

Measurement of texture

Measurement of gel strength, rupture force/rupture strength, brittleness/elasticity and adhesiveness of the prepared sample formulations was done using Texture Analyzer, TA.XT Plus (Stable Microsystems, UK)(Rahman et al., 2021, Rosenthal, 2010, Pons & Fiszman, 1996, Brandt et al., 1963). 25 mm Diameter cylinder (P/25R) using 5kg load cell was used for the test. After a trigger force of 10g is attained the probe then proceeded to penetrate into the gel to a depth of 15 mm. During penetration the force was shown to drop at the point where the gel breaks. After this, the resulting forces were due to continuing penetration up to the required depth. The maximum +ve force (i.e. the rupture point of the gel) was taken and recorded as 'rupture strength' (or 'rupture force'). The distance that the gel penetrated before this break occurred gave an indication of the gel's elasticity, i.e. a short distance of penetration before break indicated a brittle gel whereas a large distance of penetration before rupture indicated a more elastic gel. When the probe was withdrawn from the sample, the total force (area under the negative region of the curve) required to do this is

measured and recorded as the 'adhesiveness'. A 'gel strength' measurement was taken at the initial stage of penetration, i.e. a point (in this case 1.5 mm) in the penetration where little gel deformation had occurred. The settings of TA-XT Plus are given in table 3.

Table 3: TA-XT Plus Settings:

Mode:	Measure Force in Compression
Option:	Return to Start
Pre-Test Speed:	3.0 mm/s
Test Speed:	2.0 mm/s
Post-Test Speed:	10.0 mm/s
Distance:	15 mm
Trigger Type:	Auto - 10g
Data Acquisition Rate:	200 pps

The products were prepared according to the experimental plan and conditioned for 24 h at room temperature. After conditioning, the sample containers were placed centrally under the probe and the penetration test was commenced. The textural data (force vs. time) was analyzed by the instrument software (TEE 32) and parameters (gel strength, rupture force, brittleness/elasticity and adhesiveness) were recorded.

The gelling profile of the System

The **gelling/thickening profile** of a system as it is cooled from **80°C to 30°C** gives a fingerprint of that particular hydrocolloid's behaviour. This is obtained using Rapid Visco Analyser (RVA) (Techawipharat et al., 2005, Martínez, 2015). Here gelling/thickening profile (that means how the viscosity of jam varies as it is cooled) of regular jam as well as the spread preparation which was hydrocolloid-mango pulp based system had been studied as these were cooled from 80°C to 30°C. The results were analyzed using TCW software. In each case the run conditions of the RVA are given in the table 4.:

Table 4: RVA Run Conditions:

1.	Sample	25 g
2.	Cooling	From 80°C to 30°C
3.	Cooling Rate	1°C per minute after an initial holding time of 5 minutes at 80°C and 10 minutes at 30°C
4.	Speed	160 rpm throughout the test

Calorific Value

The energy value or calorific value of the jam samples were determined by **Micro Processor Based Bomb Calorimeter** (Model CC01/M3, Toshniwal, Delhi, India - Make) with software and PC. 1.0 g of sample was taken in stainless steel crucible and it was connected with ignition wire. The crucible was kept inside the bomb made up of stainless steel, capable of withstanding 400 bar pressure. The bomb was filled with oxygen gas at 40 bar pressure to oxidize the food sample. The bomb was kept inside the outer vessel already filled with water. Bomb was immersed in water. Automatic firing in the bomb was taken with the software. Rise in temperature during oxidation process was measured by the unit having a specially designed temperature measuring device capable to measure 0.001 °C. software calculated the automatic values of water equivalent and calorific value of food samples and

the data was stored in the PC.

B. Sensory evaluation

A semi-trained panel consisted of seven testers including male and female members. All evaluation sessions were held in the Food quality evaluation laboratory in H. B. T. U., Kanpur. The sensory evaluation of prepared samples was carried out after 3 days of the manufacturing. The samples were stored at 5⁰C and were taken out 3 h before serving.

Hedonic Scale Test

Color, taste, odor, texture, and overall acceptability of mango jam samples were evaluated using thenine-point hedonic scale given in table 5 (Kemp et al.,2011, Lawless & Heymann, 1998).

Table 5: Nine-point hedonic scale

Attribute	Score
Like extremely	9
Like very much	8
Like moderately	7
Like slightly	6
Neither like nor dislike	5
Dislike slightly	4
Dislike moderately	3
Dislike very much	2
Dislike extremely	1

The samples were presented before the panelists at room temperature under normal lighting conditions in 50 mL cups coded with random, three-digit numbers. Bread pieces and spoons were provided to the panelists. Drinking water was provided for oral rinsing. The average values of the sensory scores (color, taste, odor, spreadability, and overall acceptability) were used in the analysis.

Flavour Profile

Flavor profiling is a consensus technique. The vocabulary used to describe the product and the product evaluation itself is achieved by reaching agreement among the panel members. The profile describes the overall flavor and the flavor notes and estimates the intensity of these descriptors and the amplitude (overall impression). The technique provides a tabulation of the perceived flavors, their intensities, their order of perception, their aftertastes, and their overall impression (amplitude) (Lawless and Heymann, 2010, Stone et al., 2008, Cairncross & Sjostrom, 2004). The data were presented by using “cobweb” graphs or “radar” plots. The aroma and taste attributes, evaluated for profiling are described in table 6 and table 7 respectively.

Table 6: Aroma Attributes

Attribute	Description
Mango	Intensity of typical mango aroma.
Sweet	Intensity of sweet (Honey, Vanilla, Syrupy or burnt sugar) aroma.
Estery	Intensity of flavours like fresh fruits (apricot, peach, lemon, orange), dried fruits (raisins, artificial fruit flavourings), solventy (paint thinners, nail varnish remover), or soapy (unperfumed soap).
Ripe	Intensity of aroma of matured/ripe fruit.
Green	Intensity of green aroma, this can include any green plant and green unripened fruit.
Intensity	Intensity of overall aroma.
Complexity	Complexity in aromas.
Uniformity	Uniformity of aromas.

Table 7: Taste Attributes

Attribute	Description
Mango	Intensity of typical mango taste.
Sweet	Intensity of sweet taste.
Estery	Intensity of Estery (Fruity, Solventy or Soapy) taste.
Ripe	Intensity of taste of matured/ripe fruit.
Green	Intensity of green flavor, this can include any green growing thing and green un-ripened fruit.
Body	Overall mouthfeel.
Finish	Length of time the flavour lingers.
Bitter Aftertaste	Bitter aftertaste due to artificial sweetener.
Complexity	Complexity in taste.
Uniformity	Uniformity of taste.

Results and Discussions

Instrumental Analysis

Texture Analysis

The textural parameters (gel strength, rupture strength/rupture force, brittleness/elasticity and adhesiveness) of prepared samples were measured at room temperature ($25\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$) after 24 h of jam preparation, after it was fully set.

Force-Time Study for prepared samples

The force-time curves were obtained from instrument software texture exponent-32. The graphs in Fig. 3 (Sample-1: Spread containing carrageenan) and Fig. 4 (Sample-2: Regular mango jam) are force-time curves for each of the prepared samples. All the four parameters i.e. gel strength, rupture strength/rupture force, brittleness/elasticity and adhesiveness for a sample were obtained from the force-time curve itself, the values of which were automatically given by the instrument software and shown in Table 8. It can be observed from the table that the values of gel strength, rupture strength and elasticity are enough similar for both the samples but the value of adhesiveness for carrageenan sample is almost triple than that of the regular jam showing the high adhesive property of carrageenan containing spread sample.

Figure 3: Texture Analysis: Spread Sample (Sample-1) containing carrageenan

Figure 4: Texture Analysis: Regular Mango Jam (Sample-2) containing Pectin-sugar-acid gel

Table 8: Texture Analysis results obtained from prepared samples

Sample No.	Sample Description	'Gel Strength' (g)	'Rupture Strength' (g)	'Elasticity' (mm)	'Adhesiveness' (gs)
1.	Containing Carrageenan	43.50	602.40	8.90	114.15
2.	Regular jam	63.50	536.80	6.87	45.79

The gelling profile and final viscosity values of the Samples

The gelling profile

The gelling profiles of the samples are shown in fig. 5 (Sample-1: Spread containing carrageenan) and Fig. 6 (Sample-2: Regular mango jam). Each profile gives the pattern of change of viscosity of the sample as the sample is cooled from 80 °C to 30 °C with the rate of 1 °C per minute after an initial holding time of 5 minutes at 80°C and 10 minutes at 30°C. The pattern shown in the fig. 5 represents characteristic behavior of the hydrocolloid carrageenan present in the hydrocolloid-mango pulp-water based system. It showed slow increase of viscosity initially and a sudden rapid increase in viscosity between the temperature range 45 to 35°C. Regular jam profile shown in the fig. 6 represents the behavior of pectin-sugar-acid gel with the regular pattern of increase in viscosity and attaining a final high value.

Final Viscosity values of samples

Final viscosity values at 30 °C after a holding period of 10 min are given in table 9. The value of gel final viscosity for sample -1 containing carrageenan was found to be 958 cp while for the regular jam it was found as 725 cp. Thus the carrageenan sample was found very much viscous as compared to the regular jam sample.

Figure 5: The gelling/thickening profile for sample-1 containing carrageenan

Figure6: The gelling/thickening profile for pectin-sugar-acid gel in regular mango jam

Table 9: Final viscosity values of the prepared samples at 30 °C after a holding period of 10 min

Sample No.	Sample Description	Final Viscosity (CP) at 30 °C after a holding time of 10 mins
1.	Containing Carrageenan	958
2.	Regular jam	725

Calorific values

The calorific values estimated by bomb calorimeter are shown in Table 10. The calorific value was greatly reduced by about 79.65% in the spread sample prepared with carrageenan. Regular jam had a very high calorific value because of high sugar content which gives 20 kilocalories per teaspoon (5g) while in the preparation of the spread sample, the sugar free gold pellets were used as sweetener which contains aspartame. 100 mg of this sweetener is equivalent in sweetness to 5g of sugar. Thus very low amount of sweetener was needed for the preparation of spread sample which reduces the calories in a large amount. Except this the hydrocolloid carrageenan used had also very less calorific value and it was used in very less amount (2% of the pulp). Therefore, the sweetener and hydrocolloid both contributed to very less of energy value. Mango pulp itself has about 67 calories per 100g which is the main contributor of calorific value of the prepared samples of mango jam/spread.

Table 10: Calorific value and percentage reduction in calorie for spread sample

Sample No.	Sample Description	Calorific Value per 100g (Kcal) (Mean \pm SD)	% Reduction of Calories
1.	Containing Carrageenan	57.99 \pm 0.04	79.65
2.	Regular jam	284.95 \pm 0.04	

Sensory properties of the prepared samples

Hedonic Scale Test for prepared samples

Average scores of sensory attributes in respect of color, odor, taste, texture/spreadability, and overall acceptability of the prepared samples are reported in Table 11. The carrageenan sample received the overall acceptability score as 8.29 \pm 1.03 which was very similar to that of the regular jam which received the overall acceptability score as 8.86 \pm 0.35. Also for all other parameters, it showed the scores enough similar to that of regular jam.

Table 11: Results of sensory evaluation of mango jam samples

Attributes	Sample-1 Containing Carrageenan	Sample-2 Regular Mango Jam
Color (Mean \pm SD)	8.29 \pm 1.03	8.86 \pm 0.35
Odor (Mean \pm SD)	8.57 \pm 0.49	7.29 \pm 0.70

Taste (Mean ± SD)	7.86±0.64	8.00±0.76
Texture/Spreadability (Mean ± SD)	8.71±0.45	7.14±0.83
Overall Acceptability (Mean ± SD)	7.86±0.64	8.00±1.07

Flavour Profile of the prepared samples

Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 show aroma profile of the sample-1 and 2. The sample containing carrageenan was found rich in aromas and close to the regular product. Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 show taste profile of the samples. Again the sample containing carrageenan is found very close to regular jam. A slight bitter aftertaste is observed in the sample containing carrageenan because of the use of artificial sweetener. Due to sugar sweet aroma was more observed in regular jam than in carrageenan based sample.

Conclusion

Thus the preparation of no sugar added mangos spread is possible using pulp, the hydrocolloid carrageenan and low calorie sweetener aspartame. The product prepared showed very similarity to the regular product in spite of some variations in some property parameters. Textural properties showed almost similar textural characteristics except adhesiveness which was found high in carrageenan sample as compared to regular jam. Gelling study showed the higher value of viscosity in carrageenan based spread sample as compared to the control. Still the sample prepared with carrageenan secured almost similar sensory acceptability scores for overall acceptability as well as for other sensory attributes. The aroma and taste profiles of the carrageenan based spread sample were also found close to those of regular jam except some specific sensory attributes. Therefore, the mango spread can be made easily using the hydrocolloid carrageenan and may prove very helpful to diabetic patients as well as obese persons as a substitute of high sugar and high calorie regular mango jam.

Figure 7: Aroma profile of sample-1 containing carrageenan

Figure 8: Aroma profile of sample-2 Regular mango jam

Figure 9: Taste profile of sample-1 containing carrageenan

Figure 10: Taste profile of sample-2: Regular Mango Jam

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